

New Inscriptions from Nikaia XVII

Nikaia'dan Yeni Yazıtlar XVII

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Abstract: This article introduces a total of six new inscriptions discovered in the Central, Söğüt, and Yenipazar districts of Bilecik Province. In antiquity, these districts were part of the territorium of Nicaea. These funerary inscriptions are important in that they introduce us to new names that were previously unknown in the region, and they are dated mainly to the IInd-IIIrd centuries AD, the Roman Imperial period. A number of names previously documented in Anatolia or Greece were documented for the first time in the territory of Nicaea. Among these are Antandros and Thetis. It is particularly noteworthy that the name Thetis, which is not very common, appears here. Therefore, this article contains important data on the demographic structure and onomastics of the region.

Keywords: Bithynia, Nicaea, Inscription, Anthroponym

Öz: Bu makalede toplamda Bilecik ilinin Merkez, Söğüt ve Yenipazar ilçelerinde keşfedilmiş 6 yeni yazıt tanıtılmaktadır. Bu ilçeler, antik çağda Nikaia territorium'unun içinde yer almaktaydı. Söz konusu mezar yazıtları bizlere bölgede daha önceden bilinmeyen yeni isimleri bizlere tanıtması bakımından önemli olup, bunlar özellikle MS II-III. yy.lara, Roma İmparatorluk devrine tarihlenmektedir. Küçük Asya ya da Hellas'ta daha önce belgelenmiş birtakım isimlerin Nikaia territoriumunda ilk kez belgelendiği görülmüştür. Bunlar arasında Antandros ve Thetis sayılabilir. Çok fazla yaygın olmayan Thetis isminin burada karşımıza çıkması da özellikle dikkat çekicidir. Bu nedenle de bu makale, bölgenin demografik yapısına ve onomastiğine dair önemli veriler içermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Bithynia, Nikaia, Yazıt, Anthroponymos

An epigraphic-historical and geographical survey was initiated in 2010 by Hüseyin Sami Öztürk in the eastern and south-eastern part of the territory of the ancient city of Nikaia¹. As a result of this

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¹ We wish to offer our thanks to the General Directorate of Cultural Heritage and Museums - Department of Excavations and Surveys and its staff for granting the license to work in Sakarya and Bilecik provinces (Project no.: YA01541101); Marmara University BAPKO for providing financial support for this project (Project no. SOS-A-070617-0393); Ministry of Culture Representative Tuba Güler (Kütahya Museum in 2018) and Abdulkadir Şahin (Turkish Islamic Museum in 2019); and for their help to Mayor of Osmaneli District of Bilecik Province Münür Şahin, Mayor of Yenipazar District İlhan Özden, the Dost Association, formerly Director of Cultural Affairs of Osmaneli Municipality Süleyman Çakar, Yenipazar Municipality Technical Affairs staff member Hicran Kılıçarslan and team members Classical Studies specialist and epigraphist Ezgi Demirhan-Öztürk (PhD, Koç University), archaeologist Adem Gündüz and Abdurrahman Aktaş (former archaeologist at Bilecik Museum; now director of Artvin Provincial Directorate of Culture

survey, many new unpublished inscriptions are being recorded every year and the knowledge about the territory of the city of Nikaia is increasing year by year. As will be seen below, this article introduces 6 new funerary inscriptions found during the survey in the districts of Bilecik province. These inscriptions provide an opportunity to increase our knowledge about the city of Nikaia.

Epitaph of Aurelius Olympios and His Son Philon and Hypsaïos (Fig. 1a-c)

Fig. 1a.

Fig. 1b.

Fig. 1c.

Limestone funerary stele with a profiled upper section. There is a rosette centrally aligned under the profile at the top. The stele is damaged at the top left corner, middle right of the side and to a lesser extent, but longer, on the left side. The eight-line inscription is located on the southern half of the stele.

Find spot: Bilecik province Yenipazar district, Kükürt village, in Güney locality, in front of Mustafa Zengin's home.

Measurements: H: 1.08 m; W: 44.5 cm; T: 47 cm; LH: 2.1-3.5 cm

Inv. no.: 311 [2016 year]

Registration: Hüseyin Sami Öztürk - Ezgi Demirhan-Öztürk

Photo: Ezgi Demirhan-Öztürk

Date: After AD 212

Ἀὐρ(ηλίω) Ὀλυμπίω τῷ ν
 γλυκυτάτῳ ἀνδρ[ὶ νν]
 ζήσαντι ἔτη ν με' νν
 4 Ἀὐρ(ηλία) Χρήστη μνήμ[ης]
 χάριν καὶ Φίλωνι τέ-
 [κ]νῳ ἔτῶν νν ζ' vacat
 [κ]ἔ Ἀὐρ(ηλίω) Ὑψέω τέκ- [νν]
 8 [ν]ῳ ζήσαντι ἔτη ν [./..].

Aurelia Khreste erected (this tomb) for her beloved husband, Aurelius Olympios who lived for 45 years; her son Philon, who lived for 6 years and ... her son Aurelius Hypsaïos, who lived ... for years.

L. 7: Ὑψέω = Ὑψαῖος: Due to the iotacism rule, the reading -αι here has changed to -ε². The

and Tourism).

² For the interchange, see Laminger-Pascher 1973, 10.

Hypsaïos name is previously documented for the first time in Nikaia³ and the name is not quite common in Asia Minor. This name is also known only six times from Mysia, Phrygia and Pontos⁴.

By considering the fact that the inscription naming the sons separately instead of together, it is possible that the lines for Aurelius Hypsaïos was added after the stele was erected, as he could have been alive at the time of its creation. It is even possible that the stele was erected in memory of Aurelius Olympios first, and the lines for the sons added later. If that is the case, the husband died first and the stele was erected afterwards, followed by Philon's death and not before passing of Aurelius Hypsaïos.

Epitaph of Demetrios and Meilesia (Fig. 2a-e)

Fig. 2a.

Fig. 2b.

Fig. 2c.

Fig. 2d.

Fig. 2e.

It is a limestone funerary bomos with a profiled top and bottom, which has survived largely intact. The six-line inscription is located on the upper part of the façade, and there are various reliefs below the inscription. The upper left corner of the stele, the right side of the façade from the first line of the inscription to the end of the reliefs, the center of the inscription and the lower part of the reliefs are broken. The upper part of the boom and the lower profile are also partially broken. Below the inscription, on the left side, from left to right, are a spindle whorl, a comb, a mirror, two perfume bottles and a comb; on the right side, an ox's head at the top and a plow at the bottom. The upper corners of the stele have acroterae; the one on the left is broken; on the right side

³ *I.Mus. Iznik* 1235.

⁴ LGPN VA; VC s.v.

there is a relief of a six-pointed rosette between the acroterae.

Find spot: Bilecik province, Yenipazar district, Yukarıçaylı village, Çayırpınar locality. The inscription was found with Necdet Şahin's help. We offer our thanks to him.

Coordinates: 40° 12.850" N 30° 61.223" E

Measurements: H: 1.83 m; W: 81 cm; T: 50 cm; LH: 2.3-2.9 cm

Inv. no.: 430 [2019 year]

Registration: Hüseyin Sami Öztürk - Ezgi Demirhan-Öztürk

Photo: Hüseyin Sami Öztürk

Date: IInd-IIIrd century AD

Δημητρίῳ καὶ Μειλησί[α κα]-
τεσκεύασαν τὸ μνημεῖ-
ον ἴδια τέκνα Φί[λιπ]-
4 πος, Μάρκος, Δ[ημήτ]-
[ρ]ιος(?) εὐσεβίης [ἔνε]-
vacat κεν. vacat
vacat ☼ vacat

Our children Philippos, Marcus (and) Demetrios (built this tomb for us,) Demetrios(?) and Meilesia, for our piety.

L. 1: Μειλησία = Μιλησία: Due to the iotacism rule, the reading -ει here has changed to -ι⁵. This name was previously documented twice in Nikaia⁶. With this inscription, it is now documented for the third time.

L. 4-5: Δ[ημήτ]ριος(?): It is possible that one of the parents, Demetrios, names his son after himself. Hence, we suggest the name Demetrios for the completion.

Epitaph of Gauros, son of Antandros (Fig. 3a-b)

Fragment of a funerary monument made of a marble like stone from an architrave with three fasciae. The upper part of the stone, particularly the upper left one, is in worse condition, with occasional fractures. The middle and lower fascia have a large fracture to the left of the center; the lower fascia has several other fractures. The inscription is located on the upper and middle fascia, on the front façade, and the inscription is partially centered on the fasciae. All other faces are flattened. The sigma letters are facing the opposite direction.

Fig. 3a.

Fig. 3b.

⁵ For the interchange, see Gignac 1976, 190; 249.

⁶ Öztürk & Demirhan-Öztürk 2018, 87, no. 6 = Öztürk 2023, 111-112, no. 92; Öztürk & Demirhan 2016: 172-173, no. 7 = Öztürk 2023, 123-124, no. 110.

Find spot: Bilecik province, Yenipazar district. The stele is said to have been unearthed during the road construction between Yenipazar and Gölpaazarı, at a place called Sürümyolu. The stele is now in the backyard of the municipality.

Coordinates: -

Measurements: H: 220 cm; W: 111 cm; T: 48 cm; LH: 2.2-4.1 cm

Inv. no.: 410 [2018 year]

Registration: Ezgi Demirhan-Öztürk

Photo: Adem Gündüz

Date: IInd-IIIrd century AD

Γαῦρος ν Αντάνδρου ν ζήσας νν [ἔ]τη αξ΄
vacat τὸ μνημεῖον ἀνεξοδίαστὸν.

(Here lies) Gauros, son of Antandros, who lived for 61 years. This funerary monument cannot be sold!

L. 1: Γαῦρος: The name Gauros is generally recognized in Hellas, Moesia, Thrace⁷. This name is known in small numbers in the regions of Bithynia, Ionia, Mysia and Phrygia in Asia Minor⁸. It is previously documented for six times in Nikaia, with this inscription⁹, it is documented for the seventh time.

L. 1: "Αντανδρος: The name Antandros is new in Nikaia. This name has previously been documented once from Kalkhedon in Bithynia¹⁰. The name is not widely used in Asia Minor, but it has been documented seven times in Ionia, Karia and Lykia, with the exception of Bithynia.¹¹

Epitaph of Glykon and Theodotos (Fig. 4a-b)

Fig. 4a.

Fig. 4b.

Fragment of an architrave from a tomb made of marble like limestone. The three-line inscription is located on the front side and middle and lower half of the stone. The upper right and left sides of the stone are broken; the fracture on the left side has damaged the inscription on it up to the middle of the first line. However, the inscription is still legible. Since the inscription is aligned to the left, there is a gap at the end of the third line. Above the architrave fragment is a pit for an offering.

⁷ LGPN II; IIIB; IV s.v.

⁸ LGPN VA; VB; VC s.v.

⁹ LGPN VA s.v.; Öztürk & Acar 2020, 398-399, no. 2; Öztürk 2022, 53, no. 15 (corrigendum to *I.Mus. Iznik* 1358); Öztürk & Pilevneli 2012, 192, no. 4 = SEG LXII 1022 = Öztürk 2023, 80, no. 51; Öztürk 2023, 84-85, no. 56.

¹⁰ LGPN VA s.v.

¹¹ LGPN VA; VB s.v.

Find spot: The inscription was discovered and retrieved during a clean-up operation in the old cemetery of Okluca village. It is located in the Bilecik province, central district, courtyard of Okluca village mosque.

Coordinates: -

Measurements: H: 31 cm; W: 87 cm; T: 33 cm; LH: 1.6-3.3 cm

Inv. no.: 458 [2019 year]

Registration: Hüseyin Sami Öztürk - Ezgi Demirhan-Öztürk

Photo: Ezgi Demirhan-Öztürk

Date: IInd-IIIrd century AD

[Γ]λύκων Δαμᾶ ζήσας ν ἔτ ν η ν π´ ν
καὶ Θεόδοτος Γλύκωνος υἱὸς ζήσας ἔτη ν κε´
τοῖς ἐπάνω χαίρ ν ε ν ιν. vacat

(Here lies) Glykon, son of Damas, who lived for 80 years; and Theodotos, son of Glykon, who lived for 25 years. Greetings to those above the earth!

L. 1: Δαμᾶς: The name Damas is a frequently attested epichoric name in the forms Δάμας, Δάμης, Δαμοννώ, Δαμύλα, Δαμύλας¹². This name is previously documented for twice in the territory of Nikaia¹³.

Epitaph constructed by Sosandros, Papylos, Thetis, and Lucilla for their parents (Fig. 5a-c)

Fig. 5a.

Fig. 5b.

Fig. 5c.

Limestone postament erected as a funerary monument. The back and lateral sides are flattened; there is a mortise hole at the top. There is a seven-line inscription on the squareshaped front face. The first line of the inscription, which has survived intact and is separated from the rest of the inscription by a profile. The last line of the inscription is on another profile.

Find spot: Bilecik province, Cental district, Yeniköy (formerly Cedit). The inscription was found in the old cemetery of the village with the help of Mehmet Durak and Tuncay Güven. We offer our thanks to them.

Coordinates: -

Measurements: H: 64 cm; W: 51 cm; T: 47 cm; LH: 3.3-4.8 cm

Inv. no.: 422 [2018 year]

Registration: Hüseyin Sami Öztürk - Ezgi Demirhan-Öztürk

¹² See Zgusta 1964, § 250.

¹³ LGPN VA s.v. For other settlements where the name appears in Bithynia, see also LGPN VB s.v.

Photo: Adem Gündüz

Date: IInd-IIIrd century AD

Ἀγαθῆι τύχηι· vac.
 Σώσανδρος καὶ
 Παπύλ ν ος καὶ
 4 Θέτις καὶ Λουκί-
 λλα τοῖς αὐτῶν
 γονεῦσιν ἀνέστησ-
 αν μνήμης χάριν.

May there be good fortune! Sosandros, Papylos, Thetis and Lucilla erected (this funerary monument) in memory of their parents.

L. 1: Σώσανδρος: The name Sosandros is new for Nikaia and is documented for the first time in Nikaia. It was previously attested from Khios in Bithynia¹⁴.

L. 3: Παπύλος: The name Papylos is new for Nikaia and is documented for the first time in Nikaia. It was previously attested in Khios in Bithynia¹⁵.

L. 4: Θέτις: The name Thetis is new for Nikaia and is documented for the first time in Nikaia. It was previously documented only four times in Ionia, Lydia and Phrygia in Asia Minor¹⁶. The name is not very common in Asia Minor.

This is also the name of the mother of Akhilleus, one of the major characters of Homeros' Illiad and the Trojan War, where he was said to be "the greatest of all Greek warriors"¹⁷. She was the daughter of Nereus and Doris and one of the Nereids and wife of Peleus, king of Phthia¹⁸.

L. 4-5: Λουκίλλα: The name Lucilla is previously documented only once in Nikaia¹⁹. With this inscription, it is documented for the second time in Nikaia and the third time from Nikomedeia in Bithynia²⁰. This name is documented 27 times in Kabalis, Kappadokia, Kilikia, Lydia, Lykia, Paphlagonia, Phrygia, and Pisidia²¹.

Lucilla is also the name of a historical figure: This was also the name of member of Rome's Nerva Antonine Dynasty, as the second daughter of Marcus Aurelius and Faustina the Younger and elder sister of Commodus²². She was also Roman Empress during reign of her husband, Marcus Aurelius' co-ruler and adopted brother, Lucius Verus. She was executed by the order of Commodus at the age of 32-34, as she was involved in the failed coup to overthrow and replace him with her second husband and herself in 182.

The Tomb of a Person(s), whose Name(s) is/are Unknown (Fig. 6)

A funerary structure made of limestone. On the front side of the structure, there are acroterae on both sides and a rosette centered between them. The upper right and left corners of the structure and the top of the acroter on the right are broken. Below the acroterae and the rosette is a lintel

¹⁴ LGPN VA s.v.

¹⁵ LGPN VA s.v.

¹⁶ LGPN VA; VB; VC s.v.

¹⁷ Hom. *Il.* II. 236 ff.

¹⁸ A place in Thessaly, where the Thessalian tribe Myrmidons dwelled. Peleus and Akhilleus were kings of this place.

¹⁹ *I. Mus. Iznik* 1449: L. 8 ... Λούκιλλα κτλ.

²⁰ LGPN VA s.v.

²¹ LGPN VA; VB; VC s.v.

²² Dio Cass. *Ixxi* 3; *Ixxiii* 4.

like relief with a single-line, centered inscription. The lower part of the structure is largely broken.

However, a similar craftsmanship was found on the stone next to it.

Find spot: Bilecik province, Söğüt district, Kayabalı village, Ulupınar locality. The inscription was found with the headman İbrahim Gün's help. We offer our thanks to him. It is said that the stones are from Ulupınar locality as well.

Coordinates: 40° 06.663" N 30° 17.832" E

Measurements: H: 72 cm; W: 60 cm; T: 70 cm; LH: 2.8 cm

Inv. no.: 418 [2018 year]

Registration: Ezgi Demirhan-Öztürk

Photo: Adem Gündüz

Date: IInd-IIIrd century AD

Fig. 6.

vacat ἀνεξοδ[ία]στὸν vacat

(This funerary monument cannot) be sold!

L. 1: ἀνεξοδίαστὸν: This word, which means “cannot be sold” or “not for sale”, written by the owner of the tomb in order to prevent the sale of the burial, is frequently found in funerary inscriptions in the Bithynia Region, but especially in Nikaia²³.

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²³ Regarding the word, see Robert 1940, 60ff.; Kokkinia 1999, 207. For inscription examples where the word appears in Nikaia, see also, *I.Mus. Iznik* 87; 173; 283; 1231-1233; 1243; 1265; 1284; 1337; 1350; 1391-1392; 1442; 1446; 1453-1357; 1581; 1596; Öztürk 2022, 54, no. 16.

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